

1 Supplementary Materials for:

2 Protracted speciation under the state-dependent speciation and extinction approach

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5 Supplementary Figures:

6 Figure S1. Error in ML estimates of the lineage diversification rate $b - \mu$ for each simulation

7 scenario.

8 Figure S2. Error in ML estimates of the expected duration of speciation τ_{mean} for each

9 simulation scenario.

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11 Figure S1. Error in ML estimates of the lineage diversification rate $b - \mu$ for each simulation
12 scenario. Each plot of a-e) represents a value of b used in the simulation. Each facet
13 represents a value of μ used in the simulation. Each tick on x-axis represents a value of λ
14 used in the simulation. Each boxplot represents the distribution of errors, the difference
15 between the estimated and the true value of $b - \mu$ over 1000 simulated trees, showing the
16 minimum, the maximum, the median, the first and third quartiles of the distribution. In cases
17 of extreme values, boxplots are cut off for graphical readability. White boxplots are errors of
18 ProSSE estimate on lineage-level tree. Light grey boxplots are errors of constant-rate birth-
19 death model estimate on lineage-level tree. Dark grey boxplots are errors of ProSSE estimate
20 on species-level tree. Black boxplots are errors of PBD estimate on species-level tree with
21 randomly sampled lineage as the representative lineage of each species. The data for PBD is
22 from Simonet et al. (2018).

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26 Figure S2. Error in ML estimates of the expected duration of speciation τ_{mean} for each
27 simulation scenario. Each plot of a-e) represents a value of b used in the simulation. Each
28 facet represents a value of μ used in the simulation. Each tick on x-axis represents a value of
29 λ used in the simulation. Each boxplot represents the distribution of errors, the difference
30 between τ_{mean} calculated from the estimated value of b, μ, λ and the true value of b, μ, λ
31 over 1000 simulated trees, showing the minimum, the maximum, the median, the first and
32 third quartiles of the distribution. In cases of extreme values, boxplots are cut off for
33 graphical readability. White boxplots are errors of ProSSE estimate on lineage-level tree.
34 Grey boxplots are errors of ProSSE estimate on species-level tree. Black boxplots are errors
35 of PBD estimate on species-level tree with randomly sampled lineage as the representative
36 lineage of each species. The data for PBD is from Simonet et al. (2018). f) plots errors of
37 ProSSE estimate of τ_{mean} on lineage-level tree over all simulation scenarios against log tree
38 size (the number of lineages in the simulated tree on log scale), with each datapoint
39 corresponding to a simulated tree. ProSSE estimate of λ is biased for trees with more than
40 half lineages representing single-lineage species, so (f) plots trees with under and above half
41 lineages representing single-lineage species separately, with grey dots and grey boxplots for
42 trees with more than half lineages being single-lineage species and black dots and white
43 boxplots for trees with less than half lineages being single-lineage species. Boxplots in f)
44 show the distribution of errors for log tree size between 2 and 4, between 4 and 6, between 6
45 and 8, 8 and 10, and over 10.

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